

POLAND

POLAND

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN IMPROVING SOCIETY'S SPIRITUAL CAPACITY

Jabborova Saodat Sattorovna

saodatjabborova1975@mail.ru

Teacher of Turon Zarmed University,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10029177>

Abstract: This article talks about the fact that the development of spiritual potential in society is an important factor that determines the future of the country. The author provides detailed information about the system of factors forming the spiritual potential of society. It is also highlighted that the spiritual potential of modern society changes and fills up under the influence of various factors.

Key words: society, education, spiritual environment, social benefit, spiritual potential, cultural level.

The second criterion of the spiritual potential of the society - the improvement of the cultural level of the members of the society depends on the optimal content and quality of education. It is known that "the content of education includes, in addition to general knowledge, special knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for a specific profession and specialty." The quality of education is determined by the systematicity and integrity of the imparted knowledge, its structural relevance and hierarchical character, its dynamism, and its proportionality to social needs. Both of them are one of the important sources that raise the cultural level of the members of the society. "Any educational institution has the ability to have a serious educational impact on the people living in the area where it is located, to create an acceptable spiritual environment in that area. They have a priority in increasing the level of awareness of a person's socio-humanitarian, natural-scientific, mathematical and technical knowledge." As the content and quality of education in these places increases, their opportunities to influence the cultural level of the individual expand.

The experience of countries that have formed a meaningful and quality education system fully supports the above conclusions. For example, in general education schools in Finland, the main attention is focused, on the one hand, on imparting the system of knowledge necessary for life, and on the other hand, on creating the foundations of professional training of children in upper grades. This approach allows adapting the content of education to social needs and people's vital needs. The quality of education in the educational institutions of

the country is provided by imparting knowledge in an interactive way, divided into certain blocks.

Contentful and quality education leaves a significant mark on children's cultural level. "According to international studies conducted every three years by the prestigious Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, Finnish schoolchildren demonstrate the highest level of knowledge in the world. They are also the most read children in the world. In addition, Finnish schoolchildren rank second in the world in science and fifth in mathematics. The content and quality of professional education has a special role in the formation of the cultural level of society members. In countries that have developed vocational education of high content and quality, young people are able to acquire not only professional knowledge, but also information that shapes their worldview. For example, in France, all vocational training institutions are integrated into the Center de Formation d'Apprentis (CFA). This center makes it possible to optimize the content and quality of education in vocational education centers of the country in a harmonious and systematic manner. The content of education in the centers is provided through a system of theoretical training of 400-670 hours, and its quality is provided by the practice of children in enterprises. As a result, all young people who have graduated from professional educational institutions are fully mastering the secrets of certain professions.

Great Britain attracts attention with the content and quality of its higher education. Academically and financially independent higher education system has been established in the country. Institutions that are part of it provide students with absolutely meaningful and high-quality education.

This kind of education fundamentally changes the outlook and cultural level of the graduates. For the same reason, the English higher education system is accepted as a global model in all countries.

The above comments clearly show the connection in the chain of "the optimality of the content and quality of education - the cultural level of the members of the society - the spiritual potential of the society". As the content and quality of education in the society becomes optimal, the cultural level of people also increases, and this situation creates the ground for the formation and development of spiritual potential. On the contrary, meaningless and low-quality education stops people's cultural maturity and ultimately leads to a decline in the moral potential of society. Therefore, it is necessary to look for the second source of raising the spiritual potential from the optimization of the content and quality of education.

To conclude, the spiritual potential of the modern society changes and fills up under the influence of various factors. Its various criteria are the compatibility of behavioral norms in the development society with social interests, the optimal content and quality of education, the systematicity of ideological institutions, the improvement of the cultural-educational system, the proportionality of the development of science to social needs, the existence of a social order for literary and artistic masterpieces, the determination of national pride, goes back to the issues of formation of the concept of moral security.

References:

1. Авдашкин А.А., Пасс А.А. Подходы к определению понятия “качество образования”.// Научно-методическое обеспечение оценки качества образования, 2018, №2.- 22-с.
2. Соҳибова Л.Ж. Ўзбекистондаги ижтимоий жараёнларнинг шахс маданий савиясига таъсири: Фалс.д. (PhD) дисс. автореф.- Бухоро: БухДУ, 2022.- Б.15.
3. Дубаков А.В., Оларь Ю.В., Кузьменкина Е.В. Образование в Финляндии: феномен успеха.// Мир науки. Педагогика и психология, 2021, №2.- 2-с.
4. Розенфельд Ю.Н., Рощупкин Г.В. Особенности системы высшего образования в Великобритании.// Pedagogics, psychology, medical-biological problems of physical training and sports, 2006, №12.- 141-143-с.
5. Sattorovna, J. S. (2023). The Role of Spirituality in the Education of a Perfect Generation. (Комил авлод тарбиясида- маънавиятнинг ўрни) Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 4(5), 296-299. Retrieved from.
<https://cajlp.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJLPC/article/view/874>.
6. Saodat Sattorovna, Jabborova (2022) Analysis of the Idea of Freedom in Eastern and Western Philosophical Views. (Шарқ ва ғарб фалсафий қарашларида еркинлик ғоясининг таҳлили) International Journal on Integrated Education, 5 (12). pp. 307-309. ISSN 2620-3502
7. Jabborova S.S. “O‘zbekistonda jamiyatning ma’naviy salohiyati va uning ijtimoiy taraqqiyotni ta’minlashdagi roli”. FarDU ILMIIY XABARLAR 4-2023, 67 b.
8. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Manifestations of Moral Threats in the Ideosphere of Uzbekistan and Their Prevention Strategy. Asian Journal of Basic Science & Research, 5(1), 103-108.
9. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST), 7(1), 149-157.

10. Sobirovich T. B. National Revival and Development Idiosphere of Uzbekistan. – 2023.
11. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). MANIFESTATION OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE IDEOSPHERE OF UZBEKISTAN. Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects, 89-92.
12. Sobirovich, T. B., & Norman, Z. D. M. (2023). Harmony of National and Universal Values in Uzbekistan. Harmony, 7(1), 08-16.
13. Turdiyev, B. S. (2022). INTERPRETATION OF UNIVERSAL VALUES IN ZOROASTRIANISM. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 109-114. Sobirovich, T. B. Interethnic Harmony And Religious Tolerance- An Integral Part of The Ancient Traditions Of The Uzbeks.
14. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.
15. Sobirovich T. B. The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 197-202.
16. Sobirovich T. B. Issues of gender equality in uzbekistan: Strategy of reforms //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 203-207.
17. Sobirovich T. B. National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan //Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS). – 2021. – T. 5. – №. 3. – C. 131-135.
18. Sobirovich T. B. Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development //Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IIJSR). – 2021.
19. Turdiyev B. S. The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 229-233.
20. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2020. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 122-126.
21. Sobirovich T. B., Murodogli I. S. The strategy for the implementation of the modern governance system in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 5. – C. 741-748.
22. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of spiritual renewal in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – T. 24. – №. 06.